

Replication package for “Assessing Harmful Comments and Specificity in Code Review Feedback at Scale using Large Language Models”

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1 Unfurled feedback dataset schema

Field Name	Description
<code>feedback_uuid</code>	Unique identifier for the feedback instance
<code>first_comment_time</code>	Timestamp of the first comment
<code>last_comment_time</code>	Timestamp of the last comment
<code>organisation</code>	Name of the organisation
<code>repository</code>	Name of the repository
<code>pr_id</code>	Pull request identifier
<code>pr_title</code>	Title of the pull request
<code>pr_author</code>	Author of the pull request
<code>feedback_author</code>	Author of the feedback (commenter)
<code>pr_author_pronoun</code>	Pronouns of the pull request author (if provided)
<code>feedback_author_pronoun</code>	Pronouns of the reviewer (if provided)
<code>total_chars</code>	Total number of characters in the comment block
<code>comment_count</code>	Number of comments in the feedback block
<code>unfurled_feedback</code>	Concatenated comment text block

2 OSS Data Repository Sample Size Calculations

Repository	Feedback	Proportional Sample	Capped Sample
Scrcpy	174	9	100 ↑
Awesome-selfhosted	187	10	100 ↑
Axios	211	11	100 ↑
Linux	366	19	100 ↑
Bootstrap	471	25	100 ↑
Ohmyzsh	635	33	100 ↑
Stable-diffusion-webui	1074	57	100 ↑
Developer-roadmap	1317	69	100 ↑
Python	1507	79	100 ↑
Yt-dlp	1722	91	100 ↑
Typescript	2241	118	118
React-native	2257	119	119
Autogpt	2271	120	120
Powertoys	2310	121	121
Tensorflow	2369	124	124
Three.js	2378	125	125
Electron	2529	133	133
Ollama	3058	161	161
Vscode	4368	230	230
React	4504	237	237
Langchain	9136	481	400 ↓
Next.js	11010	579	400 ↓
Flutter	11092	584	400 ↓
Node	11262	592	400 ↓
Transformers	18557	975	400 ↓
Kubernetes	32603	1713	400 ↓
Rust	74680	3929	400 ↓

3 Prompt and Symbol Mappings

3.1 Sentiment Prompt Template

Extract the overall sentiment and confidence metrics from the following code review feedback:

=====

When analyzing the feedback:

[itemsep=0pt, topsep=2pt, parsep=0pt, partopsep=0pt]

1. Consider all comments as a collective code review session.
2. Identify the primary sentiment across all comments.
3. Assess your confidence in the sentiment classification.
4. Provide reasoning for your confidence assessment.
5. Rate your confidence in that reasoning.
6. If the sentiment is "banana", return one or more negativity reasons from the following list:

[itemsep=0pt, topsep=1pt, parsep=0pt, partopsep=0pt]

- Personal_Attack: Contains personal attacks directed at the PR author.
 - Vague_Criticism: Includes vague criticism with no clear suggestions.
 - Judgmental: Has a judgmental or superior tone.
 - Terseness: Feedback is overly brief or terse.
 - Excessive_Nit: Contains repeated or excessive nitpicking.
 - Harsh_Language: Uses harsh, inconsiderate, or aggressive language.
7. Otherwise, if the sentiment is "apple" or "cherry", return "Not_Negative" as the negativity reason.

3.2 Sentiment Symbol Mapping

[itemsep=0pt, topsep=2pt, parsep=0pt, partopsep=0pt]

- "apple" = Positive
- "cherry" = Neutral
- "banana" = Negative

3.3 Specificity Prompt Template

Extract the overall specificity and confidence metrics from the following code review feedback:

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When analyzing the feedback:

[itemsep=0pt, topsep=2pt, parsep=0pt, partopsep=0pt]

1. Consider all comments as a collective code review session.
2. Identify the primary specificity level across all comments.
3. Assess your confidence in the specificity classification.
4. Provide reasoning for your confidence assessment.
5. Rate your confidence in that reasoning.
6. If the specificity is "apple" or "cherry", return one or more specificity reasons from the following list:
 - `Specific_Suggestion_With_Reasoning`: Specific suggestion with reasoning or justification.
 - `Specific_Suggestion_Without_Reasoning`: Specific suggestion without reasoning or justification.
 - `Thought_Provoking_Question`: Thought-provoking question or comment.
 - `Link_Or_Code_With_Reasoning`: Link or code suggestion with reasoning or justification.
 - `Link_Or_Code_Without_Reasoning`: Link or code suggestion without reasoning or justification.
7. Otherwise, if the specificity is "banana", return "Not_Specific" as the specificity reason.

3.4 Specificity Symbol Mapping

[itemsep=0pt, topsep=2pt, parsep=0pt, partopsep=0pt]

- "apple" = Highly Specific
- "cherry" = Neutral Specificity
- "banana" = Highly Unspecific

3.5 Model Output Fields for the Sentiment Experiment

Field	Description
prediction_sentiment_label	Predicted sentiment label
negative_reason_bucket	Reason for negative sentiment
prediction_sentiment_confidence	Model confidence for sentiment
sentiment_label_reason	Explanation for predicted sentiment
model_name	LLM that generated the annotation

3.6 Model Output Fields for the Specificity Experiment

Field	Description
prediction_specificity_label	Predicted specificity label
specificity_reason_bucket	Reason for specificity label
prediction_specificity_confidence	Model confidence for specificity
specificity_label_reason	Explanation for predicted specificity
is_minimal	Whether the feedback is minimal
model_name	LLM that generated the annotation